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Encoding manual dexterity through modulation of intrinsic alpha band connectivity

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1 **Title: Encoding manual dexterity through modulation of intrinsic alpha**
2 **band connectivity**

3 **Abbreviated title: Encoding manual dexterity in the brain at rest**

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42 **Abstract**

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44 The human hand possesses both consolidated motor skills and remarkable flexibility in adapting to
45 ongoing task demands. However, the underlying mechanisms by which the brain balances stability
46 and flexibility remain unknown. In the absence of external input or behavior, spontaneous (intrinsic)
47 brain connectivity is thought to represent a prior of stored memories. In this study, we investigated
48 how manual dexterity modulates spontaneous functional connectivity in the motor cortex during hand
49 movement. Using magnetoencephalography (MEG), in 47 human participants (both sexes) we
50 examined connectivity modulations in the alpha and beta frequency bands at rest and during two
51 motor tasks (*i.e.*, finger tapping or toe squeezing). The flexibility and stability of such modulations
52 allowed us to identify two groups of participants with different levels of performance (*High* and *Low*
53 *performers*) on the 9-hole peg test, a test of manual dexterity. In the alpha band, participants with
54 higher manual dexterity showed distributed decreases of connectivity, specifically in the motor
55 cortex, increased segregation, and reduced nodal centrality. Participants with lower manual dexterity
56 showed an opposite pattern. Notably, these patterns from the brain to behavior are mirrored by results
57 from behavior to the brain. Indeed, when participants were divided using the median split of the
58 dexterity score, we found the same connectivity patterns. In summary, this experiment shows that a
59 long-term motor skill –manual dexterity– influences the way the motor systems respond during
60 movements.

61 **Significance statement**

62 Using hands efficiently is central to our daily life. Importantly, however, individuals differ in manual
63 dexterity. We study whether the brain's functional organization encodes variability in manual
64 behavior. Using a large set of MEG data acquired during rest and a finger-tapping task, we
65 investigated how hand movements change the intrinsic functional connectivity and network
66 architecture. Specifically in the alpha band, we demonstrate that higher dexterity is associated with
67 decreased connectivity, specifically in the motor cortex, increased segregation, and reduced nodal

68 centrality. Low-dexterous individuals show opposite patterns. We concluded that manual dexterity
69 influences how the motor system responds during movements. These findings yield high potential to
70 understand how intrinsic connectivity retains relevant behavior and to develop neural biomarkers of
71 pathological behavior.

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73 **Introduction**

74
75 Healthy individuals differ in their manual dexterity. This ability is fundamental to efficiently interact
76 with the environment. There is evidence that manual dexterity correlates with structural and
77 functional changes of the motor cortex. For instance, keyboard and string players have larger primary
78 motor cortex (Amunts et al., 1997), grey matter density (Gaser and Schlaug, 2003; Han et al., 2009)
79 and an extension of the sensory representation of the digits (Elbert et al., 1995; Elbert and Rockstroh,
80 2004) than non-expert individuals. Furthermore, the anterior corpus callosum is larger in experts than
81 naïve (Schlaug et al., 1995), likely representing a morphological substrate of increased
82 interhemispheric communication subserving hand motor sequences. Finally, motor experts activate
83 the motor cortex more focally and efficiently (Pascual-Leone et al., 1995; Krings et al., 2000).
84 However, less is known on how the functional organization of the brain correlates with long-term
85 motor skills.

86 One leading hypothesis is that brain networks at rest (denoted resting state networks - RSNs)
87 are sculpted over the lifespan of an individual by previous experiences and learning (Albert et al.,
88 2009; Lewis et al., 2009; Ma et al., 2011; Taubert et al., 2011). Specifically, RSNs may represent a
89 mechanism for storing and keeping on-line behaviorally relevant representations (Pezzulo et al.,
90 2021). However, to our knowledge, no study to date has shown that long-term motor skills are already
91 encoded in task-evoked changes of intrinsic activity and that such changes influence oncoming
92 behavior.

93 Intrinsic activity is both stable and flexible. Its topography is stable across participants and
94 recording sessions (Damoiseaux et al., 2006) and resilient across behavioral states and levels of
95 consciousness (Greicius et al., 2008; Betti et al., 2013, 2018; Cole et al., 2014; Krienen et al., 2014;
96 Spadone et al., 2015). On the other hand, performing a task modifies the strength of the intrinsic
97 functional connectivity (Lewis et al., 2009; Tambini et al., 2010; Betti et al., 2013, 2018; Harmelech
98 and Malach, 2013; Cole et al., 2014; Spadone et al., 2015), and these changes can last for over a week
99 after learning (Taubert et al., 2011). This malleability meets the requirement of flexibility. Flexibility

100 means that connections that are highly correlated during resting state change their strength, frequency
101 content, or topological organization during a motor task. Stability makes the functional organization
102 between rest and task performance highly similar. In this study, we tested the hypothesis that the
103 differences in dexterity may rely upon patterns of stability and flexibility of neural communication,
104 especially within the motor system.

105 Flexibility is a fundamental mechanism allowing adaptive behavior and learning (Bassett et
106 al., 2011). In terms of brain connectivity it requires both segregation (*i.e.*, independent processing in
107 specialized networks) and integration (*i.e.*, communication among networks) (Bassett et al., 2011,
108 2015; Favaretto et al., 2021). Crucially, a dynamic balance of segregation and integration is critical
109 for normal behavior (Fornito et al., 2012; Shine et al., 2016). In addition, learning (*e.g.*, motor learning
110 (Bassett et al., 2015) can modulate the underlying topology, *e.g.*, modularity (decomposability into
111 distinct partitions of the network) and hub centrality (the role of highly interconnected regions) of the
112 brain.

113 Here, we study how brain networks measured with MEG in healthy volunteers change from
114 a rest condition to perform motor tasks (hand or foot movements). Brain networks are characterized
115 in alpha and beta bands both in terms of large-scale connectivity (*e.g.*, strength, frequency content)
116 and architecture (*i.e.*, integration/segregation). Then, we employ a data-driven analysis to characterize
117 the individual variability of MEG connectivity changes and identify two groups of subjects. Finally,
118 we relate these different connectivity profiles to manual dexterity measured on a speeded visuo-motor
119 reaction time task (9-hole peg test). Specifically in the alpha band, we find that individuals with higher
120 dexterity show increased segregation/modularity and decreased nodal centrality when going from rest
121 to movement, especially in the motor cortex and dorsal attention network. Opposite patterns were
122 found in individuals with low dexterity. These results show that pre-existent manual ability influences
123 the way the motor cortex reorganizes during ongoing task demands.

124 **Materials and Methods**

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126

127 ***Participants***

128

129 We analyzed Magnetoencephalography (MEG) data from 47 participants (mean age \pm s.d. = $27.8 \pm$
130 3.8 yo, 25 F, 22 M), a subset of the freely available data collected as part of the Human Connectome
131 Project release (HCP S1200 Release - WU-Minn HCP Consortium). Among the available HCP data,
132 we considered right-handed participants (mean handedness score = 79.04 ± 18.76) having both rest
133 and task blocks and which satisfied minimal criteria for data quality (see below). HCP data were
134 acquired using protocols approved by the Washington University institutional review board. Informed
135 consent was obtained from all subjects. Anonymized data are publicly available from ConnectomeDB
136 (<https://db.humanconnectome.org>).

137

138 ***Experimental design and statistical analysis***

139 MEG data were acquired with a MAGNES 3600 scanner system with 248 channels (4D
140 Neuroimaging, San Diego, CA, USA), at a sampling rate of 2034.5 Hz. Subjects were first recorded
141 during three blocks of visual fixation (rest), each lasting 6 minutes, and then during two runs of three
142 types of tasks, the latter of which consisted of a motor task lasting 14 minutes (Larson-Prior et al.,
143 2013). The motor task started after about a 10 minute break, during which EMG electrodes were
144 mounted. During the motor task, participants were presented with visual cues providing instructions
145 about the movement to perform with their right or left hand or right and left foot. The hand movements
146 consisted in a finger tapping task involving the thumb and the index finger, whereas for the foot
147 condition they performed toes squeezing. The design of the motor task (Fig. 1A) included 32
148 movement blocks, 8 for each hand and foot lasting 12 seconds and 10 interleaved fixation blocks
149 lasting 15 seconds. Each movement block was composed by a 3 second cue suggesting participants
150 the next movement to perform followed by a 1050 ms black screen period. Then 10 repetitions of
151 visual pacing stimuli lasting 150 ms indicated the beginning of the movement followed by a 1050 ms
152 black screen period in which the movement should be performed. MEG data were recorded together
153 with 4 Electromyography (EMG) channels, placed on each hand and foot, 2 Electrooculography

154 (EOG) channels, and 1 Electrocardiography (ECG) channel. The HCP database also provides pre-
155 processed individual anatomical models computed from structural Magnetic Resonance Imaging
156 (MRI), necessary for source reconstruction. We used the 9-Hole peg test scores (provided by the
157 HCP) for assessing manual dexterity (Gershon et al., 2010). The dexterity scores consist of the time
158 in seconds employed to perform the test with the dominant hand. Notably, such a test is a simple and
159 low-cost measure with high test-retest reliability (Wang et al., 2015), as recently shown also on a
160 sample of HCP participants (Ruck and Schoenemann, 2021), thus representing a stable and long-term
161 individual trait.

162

163 *MEG data preprocessing and BLP estimation*

164

165 MEG data released under the WU-Minn HCP project includes unprocessed channel-level signals,
166 channel-level preprocessed and source level processed functional data, together with individual
167 anatomical data. Here, we used channel-level preprocessed resting state data (Larson-Prior et al.,
168 2013). Data in the unprocessed format were used for the motor task or when the processed data still
169 contained artifacts. For these data, we applied the same preprocessing pipeline which produced the
170 resting state data, to allow a reliable comparison among conditions. A brief description of the pre-
171 processing pipeline is reported in the following. As a first step, data were band-passed (1.3-150 Hz)
172 and notch-filtered (59-61/119-121 Hz). Then, channels and signal segments contaminated by large
173 artifacts (*i.e.*, excess residual noise in the shielded room or to muscular artifacts) were automatically
174 identified and removed from further analysis. Specifically, noisy channels were identified through
175 the low signal similarity with neighbors, measured through correlation and variance ratio, and through
176 the deviation from the distribution of channel weights obtained by an Independent Component
177 Analysis (ICA)-based approach (using FastICA with deflation approach). Then, we applied again the
178 same ICA approach on sensor space MEG signals to identify environmental, physiological (*e.g.*,
179 cardiac, ocular) and residual channel artifacts, and brain independent components (brain ICs) from

180 sensor space MEG signals, as in (Pasquale et al., 2010; Mantini et al., 2011; Betti et al., 2013). ICA
181 separation was applied 20 times from different initial conditions. The independent components (IC)
182 were automatically classified as brain or artifact for each of these iterations. For the classification, we
183 used 6 parameters: 1) correlation of the IC Time-Course with those of EOG and ECG channels filtered
184 as the MEG data; 2) correlation of the IC Power-Spectral Density (PSD) with those of EOG and ECG
185 channels; 3) correlation of the IC Power Time-Course (PTC) with those of EOG and ECG channels;
186 4) temporal kurtosis; 5) 1/f trend of the IC PSD; 6) flatness of the IC PSD. If none of these parameters
187 was above the related thresholds (which are set within the HCP script after a ROC analysis over a set
188 of independent HCP runs), then the IC was flagged as brain IC. The decomposition resulting in the
189 highest number of brain ICs and the lowest level of artifact residual contamination (measured through
190 the average (across the ICs) correlation between the brain ICs and the EOG/ECG channels) was
191 retained as the best iteration and considered for successive steps. In our analysis, the same operator
192 visually inspected the classification of the best iteration for resting state and task data, before
193 proceeding.

194 The sensor maps of the brain IC were scaled to norm 100 and then projected in the source
195 space by means of a Tikhonov-regularized Minimum-Norm Estimator (MNE). The source space
196 consisted of the individual surface-registered cortical sheet comprising 8004 vertices. The noise level
197 used by the WMNLS estimator was set to 8% of the maximum weight amplitude for each IC. We
198 limited the analysis to a subset of the original 8004 vertices, comprising functionally relevant nodes.
199 Specifically, we considered the parcellation of 164 Region of Interest (ROIs), consisting of vertices
200 belonging to 10 networks depicted in Fig. 1B (Pasquale et al., 2021). We then applied a leakage-
201 correction approach to the IC source-space maps. Leakage is inevitable due to the application of
202 projection schemes to solve the ill-posed inverse problem in MEG. Leakage typically yields a
203 spatially blurred representation of the underlying source distribution. Thus, source-space leakage
204 effects lead to the spurious co-dependence of reconstructed sources, which heavily affects
205 connectivity analysis. Hence, before estimating the functional connectivity, we applied the Geometric

206 Correction Scheme (GCS) (Wens et al., 2015) as in (Betti et al., 2018), where all the related formulas
207 are reported. The GCS is a pairwise approach, *i.e.*, it models and removes the leakage spreading from
208 a source vertex towards all other vertices based on the forward and inverse models. For each seed
209 source, the vector activity of all the other vertices in the set was estimated as the linear combination
210 of the brain IC time courses multiplied by the related leakage-corrected source space weights. For
211 both experimental conditions, we then estimated the Band Limited Power (BLP) time courses as the
212 mean of the activity square module over a sliding window lasting 400 ms, with a sampling rate equal
213 to 50 Hz.

214 We restricted our analysis to the alpha (8-15 Hz), beta low (15-26 Hz), and beta high (26-35 Hz)
215 bands, filtering the vector activity using separate high-pass and low-pass Butterworth filters. This
216 choice was driven by previous studies showing that these frequency bands represented the
217 neurophysiological correlates of RSNs (de Pasquale et al., 2010; 2012; Betti et al., 2013; Betti et
218 al., 2018). The definition of the specific frequency ranges was based on the HCP manual and pipelines.
219 Since the individual alpha peak occurred at frequency values larger than 10 Hz, the limits of this
220 interval corresponded to the -3dB value of the adopted high and low pass filters. This is also in line
221 with previous literature for networks different from the MN (Spadone et al., 2021).

222 For the motor task only, we removed the evoked activity before BLP estimation, as in the following.
223 For each direction of the vector activity of each vertex, we first averaged signals over epochs lasting
224 800 ms. The epoch onsets corresponded to the EMG trigger stored in the HCP database. We then
225 applied the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization approach as in (Penna et al., 2004), retaining the residual
226 signal for the BLP time course estimation.

227

228 *Estimation of BLP Functional Connectivity*

229

230 The static functional connectivity between a couple of nodes i and j was assessed as follows:

231

232 $FC(i, j) = NaN$ if $d(i, j) \leq 35mm$

233 or

234 $FC(i, j) = \left\{ \frac{corr(BLP(i, i), BLP(j, i)) + corr(BLP(j, j), BLP(i, j))}{2} \right\}$ if $d(i, j) > 35mm$

235

236 where $corr(x, y)$ is the Pearson's correlation coefficient between signals x and y , d_{ij} is the Euclidean
237 distance between ROIs i and j , and NaN is a "not a number" element for masking correlation
238 coefficients closer than 35 mm. This mask was applied because GCS could be affected by local mis-
239 correction effects, due to seeds mislocalization (Wens et al., 2015). The element $BLP(i, j)$ represents
240 the BLP of ROI i after removing the bias due to the leakage spread from ROI j and the diagonal
241 element $BLP(i, i)$ represents the uncorrected BLP of node i . We computed the average of the two
242 pairwise correlations to account for slight asymmetries induced by possible numerical errors.

243 For each run of rest data, the static connectivity was computed over the entire session as the average
244 of the Pearson's correlation over non-overlapping windows lasting 25 s. For the motor task, the static
245 connectivity was computed over 12 s BLP concatenated segments belonging to the same class of
246 movements. After averaging the interaction matrices across runs, we obtained for each experimental
247 condition individual and group-level static correlation matrices (Fig. 1C). To normalize the data, we
248 computed the z-fisher transform of the correlation data at the subject level.

249 *Analysis of network architecture*

250

251 To investigate putative changes of the global functional architecture induced by switching from rest
252 to the two motor tasks, the correlation matrices obtained for every subject and experimental condition
253 were analyzed with the Network-Based Statistics (NBS) toolbox separately for each band. NBS is a
254 statistical nonparametric technique that operates directly on raw connectivity values and seeks to
255 identify potential connected structures formed by a set of suprathreshold links (graph components)
256 (Zalesky et al., 2010). For the comparison between fixation and hands/feet movement, and between
257 High and Low performers (see next subsection), changes in graphs components were tested by using

258 a range of primary (t-statistic) thresholds, ranging from 5 to 9. Permutation testing (n=5000) was then
259 used to ascribe a p-value. Each component identified by NBS satisfied $p \leq 0.05$. For the graph
260 visualization, we used the MATLAB toolbox BrainNet Viewer (Xia et al., 2013). For each band, we
261 then counted the relative number of connections changed within the network, across networks and
262 for each network. Then, we analyzed possible links between the correlation changes and behavior.
263 To this aim, according to clustering indices obtained from a K-means algorithm, we split our sample
264 into two groups, comparing the task vs rest differences. Finally, we counted the number of component
265 links modified within and across networks. We are aware that the choice of this threshold certainly
266 influences the size of the obtained components also due to the contribution of false positive links in
267 a component (Zalesky et al., 2010). Nevertheless, we here computed the percentage of modified links
268 involving each RSN, normalized by their total number to compensate for the effect of false positive
269 links.

270

271 *Regression model task-rest and clustering algorithm*

272

273 For each subject, band, and network we aimed at estimating at which extent intrinsic connectivity
274 predicted task connectivity. First, for each RSN we considered all within and across-network
275 connections. Then, we adopted the following linear model for the task vs rest connectivity for each
276 RSN (Tommasin et al., 2018):

277

$$T = \beta R + \epsilon,$$

278 where T is the BLP connectivity for the motor task, R is the BLP connectivity during rest, β is the
279 slope of the linear model, and ϵ is the error. We used all the pairwise connectivity values of each RSN
280 to estimate β . This provides, for each subject and frequency band, a matrix of β (network x network).
281 Specifically, β_{ij} close to or different from 1 signaled respectively similarity or dissimilarity between
282 rFC and tFC for the across-RSN interaction involving RSN i and j. Then, we used a data driven
283 approach running a K-means algorithm on the individual beta matrices to cluster them (Fig 1D). To

284 estimate the optimal number of clusters, we varied the number of clusters from 2 to 10 choosing the
285 best value as the one producing the maximum average value of the silhouette (Kaufman and
286 Rousseeuw, 1990) provided that its values were always positive (Fig. 3-1). We then analyzed the link
287 between the clusters and the manual dexterity through t-test comparisons.

288

289 *Analysis of segregation/integration*

290

291 We then investigated possible links between the individual manual skill and the task-induced
292 modulations of the segregation/integration balance. First, the individual BLP connectivity matrices
293 were transformed into binary graphs according to a percolation analysis (Pasquale et al., 2021)
294 looking for the maximum threshold ensuring the fully connectedness of the graph (*i.e.*, the number
295 of graph components was equal to the graph size). Then, we applied Louvain modularity, as
296 implemented in BCT (Brain Connectivity Toolbox (Rubinov and Sporns, 2010) to estimate the global
297 modularity for each subject and condition (rest, hand motor task). The Louvain modularity was
298 estimated 10000 times for each subject, retaining the maximum modularity value together with the
299 corresponding modules. We then applied a mixed ANOVA with condition (Rest, Motor Task) and
300 subject group (according to the clustering results) as factors. Duncan post hoc was applied to
301 significant effects. In addition to segregation analysis, we also investigated how the motor task
302 modulated the central role of networks and hubs. Thus, for each cluster, the nodal participation index
303 (PI) was estimated over the modules in each condition. The PI values were analyzed at the RSN level,
304 through the mean PI over the nodes in each RSN, and at the nodal level. In the first case, we analyzed
305 possible differences in the participation index across groups, conditions and RSN through a mixed
306 ANOVA, with Duncan post-hoc for the analysis of significant effects. Finally, at the nodal level, we
307 ran a t-test comparing task and rest conditions in each group ($p < 0.05$). Nodes significantly changing
308 their participation index were displayed on the cortex through BrainNet Viewer.

309

310 **Results**

311 *Hand movements decrease the strength of functional connectivity.*

312 In analogy with previous studies (Betti et al., 2013; Cole et al., 2014; Krienen et al., 2014; Spadone
313 et al., 2015), we found that the execution of motor tasks preserved the overall topography of MEG
314 connectivity across all RSNs. The observed similarity (Mantel test, $p < 0.05$, $r > 0.83$) between rest and
315 motor tasks indicates a similar functional architecture across conditions (Fig. 2-1). Next, we
316 investigated the influence of movements (hand, foot) on intrinsic FC (rest). Since all subjects were
317 right-handed, we focused our analysis on the right hand, considering the left hand as a control.

318 We ran a repeated measures ANOVA with band (α , low β , high β), condition (right hand-rest vs. foot-
319 rest), and network (all RSNs) as within-subject factors on the connectivity modulation (task-rest)
320 averaged across connections of each RSN. Right hand (Fig. 2A) and foot movements (Fig. 2-3A)
321 induced an overall decrement of connectivity across all RSNs and bands. Specifically, we found a
322 significant main effect of band ($F_{2,92} = 12.14$, $p = 0.000021$, $\eta^2 = 0.21$) with smaller decrements in α
323 as compared to all other bands (mean $FC_{\alpha} = -1.55$, $FC_{\beta_{low}} = -3.73$, $FC_{\beta_{high}} = -2.50$, post hoc
324 Duncan corrected, $p = 0.000058$ and $p = 0.036$, respectively). There was also a significant main effect
325 of condition ($F_{1,46} = 6.03$, $p = 0.018$, $\eta^2 = 0.12$) with stronger decrements during foot as compared to
326 right hand movement (mean $FC_{right\ hand} = -2.22$, mean $FC_{feet} = -2.97$; $p_{Bonf} = 0.018$) (Fig. 2A and 2-
327 3A). Furthermore, we found a significant effect of network ($F_{9,414} = 11.77$, $p = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-16}$, $\eta^2 = 0.20$)
328 as well as an interaction band x network ($F_{18,828} = 7.25$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.14$) due to a weaker
329 decrement in the motor network in the alpha band ($FC_{\alpha MN} = -1.29$) as compared to the low beta
330 ($FC_{\beta_{low} MN} = -3.69$) ($p_{Bonf} = 0.00001$) and high beta bands ($FC_{\beta_{high} MN} = -2.67$) ($p_{Bonf} = 0.000017$).
331 Finally, all the other interactions were significant (all p-values < 0.05) except for band x condition.

332 As a control analysis, we ran the same repeated measures ANOVA on the task performed with the
333 left hand (Fig. 2-2A). Again, we found a significant main effect of band ($F_{2,92} = 13.44$, $p = 0.000008$,
334 $\eta^2 = 0.23$), with α connectivity values higher than all other bands (mean $FC_{\alpha} = -1.42$, $FC_{\beta_{low}} = -$
335 3.88 , $FC_{\beta_{high}} = -2.73$, post hoc Duncan corrected, $p = 0.00005$ and $p = 0.007$ respectively). We found

336 a trend for the main effect of condition ($F_{1,46} = 3.97, p = 0.05$) with decrements during feet movements
337 slightly higher compared to left hand movements (mean $FC_{left\ hand} = -2.39$, mean $FC_{feet} = -2.97$).
338 Once again, we found a significant interaction band x network ($F_{18,828} = 6.89, p = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-16}, \eta^2 =$
339 0.13) due to a weaker decrement in the motor network in the alpha band ($FC_{\alpha MN} = -1.18$) as
340 compared to the low beta ($FC_{\beta low MN} = -3.86$) ($p_{Bonf} = 0.00001$) and high beta bands ($FC_{\beta high MN} = -$
341 2.98) ($p_{Bonf} = 5 \cdot 10^{-9}$). All other interactions were significant except for band x condition and condition
342 x network (all p-values < 0.05).

343 To summarize, in agreement with previous MEG reports on visual stimuli (Betti et al., 2013,
344 2018), all RSNs decreased their connectivity during task (motor) performance, despite maintenance
345 of the overall resting-state topography. Functional connectivity decrements spread along the entire
346 cortical mantle and were stronger for foot than hand movements. Interestingly, α band decrements
347 were less prominent than in other bands, especially in the motor network.

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353 *Reorganization of network topology during finger tapping*

354

355 Next, we investigated changes of functional topology induced by the two motor tasks by means of
356 Network-based Statistics (NBS (Zalesky et al., 2010)). Figure 2B shows graph components that
357 significantly decreased for each frequency band for the right-hand movement (see Figure 2-2B for
358 the left hand). In the α band, the task produced a high proportion of decreased connections ($n=121$),
359 especially in the motor network (namely 23%, computed as the ratio between the number of changed
360 connections within the motor network divided by the total number of changed connections) (Fig. 2B,
361 upper panel, green lines). Differently, in the low β band, while a larger number of connections
362 (namely 1303, about 1 order of magnitude larger than in the alpha band) were also reduced, we did

363 not observe a predominant proportion involving the motor network (only 8%) (Fig. 2B middle panel).
364 The same applies to the high β band, where we observed an intermediate number of decreased
365 connections (namely 213, see Fig. 2B lower panel). In this case, the percentage contribution within
366 the motor network was 4%. To illustrate the contribution of each RSN, Fig. 2C shows the between-
367 (grey) and within-network (color-coded) connections. It can be noted that, only in the alpha band, we
368 observed a predominant contribution of within connections of the motor networks. In the other bands,
369 changes were more uniformly distributed across RSNs.

370

371 As a control, we performed, separately, the same analyses for toe squeezing and for finger tapping
372 performed with the left hand. Results on the left hand mirrored the ones found on the right hand,
373 supporting a larger modulation within the motor network in the α band (Fig. 2-2B-C). As before, in
374 the β bands (Fig. 2-2C, middle and lower panel), we found a modulation of network topology
375 involving all RSNs.

376 In general, foot movements re-organized many connections in all bands (Fig. 2-3). This was further
377 corroborated by NBS analysis comparing the two motor tasks with rest (hand-rest vs foot-rest).
378 Among these decreased connections, the vast majority involved connections between networks with
379 a small contribution of links within the motor network (Fig. 2-4). In summary, motor tasks induce an
380 extensive topological reorganization in both β bands. For the hand movement, it involved
381 predominantly the motor network in the α band.

382

383 *The modulation of alpha band connectivity encodes manual dexterity*

384

385 To test the behavioral relevance of intrinsic connectivity modulation in the motor cortex, we tested
386 its relationship to manual dexterity, as measured by the 9-hole peg test.

387 First, to evaluate the similarity between FC at rest (rFC) and during the task (tFC), we adopted a linear
388 model: $tFC = \beta \times rFC + e$ (Fig. 1D) and we studied the variations of β values (*i.e.*, the slope).

389 Specifically, for every RSN, we considered its set of connections (both within and across RSNs) and
390 from them we estimated the β values. This provides, for each subject and frequency band, a matrix
391 of β , with β_{ij} representing the relationship tFC-rFC between network i and j . Specifically, the larger
392 is the distance of β_{ij} from one, the higher the change from rFC to tFC. Hence for each participant, we
393 obtained a specific profile of functional reorganization between rest and task. Then, subjects were
394 clustered based on their β profiles using a K-mean clustering. We selected the number of clusters
395 based on the maximum average value of the silhouette (Kaufman and Rousseeuw, 1990). For the α
396 band, the optimal number of clusters was two (Fig. 3-1).

397 We then analyzed the link between the clusters and the manual dexterity through t-test comparisons.
398 The centroids of the obtained clusters, *i.e.*, the average of the β matrices within each class, are shown
399 in Figure 3A. In the first group (Fig. 3A left panel), β values were smaller than 1 (mean value=0.77),
400 suggesting changes of the considered connections between task and rest. By contrast, in the other
401 cluster (Fig. 3A right panel), β values were closer to 1 (mean value = 1.16), suggesting a higher
402 similarity between rFC and tFC. This different trend in the two groups is evident in Figure 3B, where
403 we report the complete β pattern for each subject in the two groups. Then, we tested whether the two
404 groups reflected a different behavioral performance, as investigated through the manual dexterity task
405 (*i.e.*, the 9-hole peg test). Interestingly, we obtained a significant difference in terms of dexterity (t_{45}
406 = -2.80, $p=0.008$). The first group was characterized by faster reaction times (mean RT \pm s.d. = 95.70
407 \pm 10.85 s) (*i.e.*, *High performers*), while the second one showed slower reaction times (mean RT \pm
408 s.d. = 103.60 \pm 8.48 s) (*i.e.*, *Low performers*) (Fig. 3C). Of note, these differences cannot be ascribed
409 to either demographic or cognitive differences, as reported in Table 3-2 (upper part). Specifically, the
410 cognitive differences were tested through a Flanker test, provided by the HCP database. Notably, this
411 result was specific for the α band. We did not obtain any significant clustering either in low or high
412 β bands (see Table 3-1).

413 In the α band, we then tested the stability of the β values and the related clustering when pruning, at
414 increasing levels, the original set of connections, to assess which was the range of connections mainly

415 driving the classification. To do so, we thresholded the connectivity matrices preserving only
416 connections above a N percentile value (see Table 3-1), from N = 0 to N = 0.99. We then computed
417 again β values for each network subset and we repeated K-means clustering. Our results demonstrate
418 that the algorithm separates two groups, only for connections not exceeding the 85th percentile. The
419 two groups could not be separated when looking at the strongest connections (>85th percentile).
420 However, the characterization of these connections is beyond the scope of this paper. The analysis
421 shown in Table 3-1 suggests that the clustering results are consistent and reproducible with respect
422 to the choice of the adopted thresholds. Notably, the same analyses did not produce any consistent
423 results neither in β low nor beta β frequency bands.
424 In summary, this analysis shows that the modulation of functional connectivity, in the α band, encodes
425 the behavioral performance.

426

427 *Differences in brain connectivity between high and low dexterity participants*

428 Figure 4A shows different patterns of FC modulation in going from rest to task (finger tapping) in
429 *High* and *Low performers*. *High performers* show an overall significant decrease of connectivity
430 across all RSNs (Fig. 4A, left). Conversely, *Low performers* display a general significant increase of
431 FC strength involving all RSNs, apart from MN and DAN (Fig. 4A, right). Second, we tested,
432 separately for the two groups, which graph components were modulated by finger-tapping. As shown
433 in Figure 4B (upper panel), participants with higher dexterity showed significant decrements of
434 correlation mainly between networks. On the contrary, *Low performers* showed significant
435 increments of correlation, both between- and within-network (lower panel).

436 To further validate this relationship between modulations of FC and dexterity (from brain to
437 behavior), we first divided participants based on their performance, and then we analyzed the
438 connectivity modulations (Fig. 4C) (from behavior to brain). We adopted a median split approach to
439 obtain *High* and *Low performers* (based on RTs on the 9-hole peg test), as shown in Figure 4D. Then,
440 as in the previous analysis (Fig. 4A), we compared the FC modulations within these two groups. In

441 agreement with the first analysis, *High performers* show large FC decrements across all RSNs,
442 differently from *Low performers* characterized by smaller FC changes (Fig. 4C). Again, these
443 differences cannot be ascribed to either demographic or cognitive differences, as reported in Table 3-
444 2.

445 The brain-to-behavior approach shows a specificity attributed to the alpha band (as revealed
446 through the clustering approach). To test this specificity also in the behavior-to-brain approach, we
447 considered the division of *High* and *Low* performers obtained from the median split. Then, we tested
448 the similarity of their connectivity modulation matrices in the alpha, beta-low, and beta-high bands,
449 across subjects through an unpaired t-test ($\alpha = 0.05$, two-tailed test). In the alpha band, we
450 obtained that a large number of connectivity changes resulted significantly different between the two
451 groups. Conversely, both in the beta low and high, this number was highly reduced (around 40% of
452 the connection changes observed in alpha). This suggests a higher similarity in the two groups in the
453 beta as compared to the alpha band. In this band, in the *High performers*, we observed an overall
454 reorganization involving all RSNs. This pattern was completely different in the beta bands, where we
455 observed changes involving only VFN, VPN, and DAN networks (Fig. 4-1). This seems to suggest a
456 specificity for the alpha band and also for the behavior-to-brain approach.

457 It must be considered that these analyses address the link connectivity-behavior from two
458 opposite perspectives: from the FC to behavior and the other way around. Thus, in the first case, the
459 connectivity modulations in the two groups are naturally enhanced, being optimized by the clustering,
460 while the resulting group division is somehow smoother. In the second analysis, instead, the groups
461 are more clearly distinguished, being separated by the median split, while the corresponding
462 differences in FC modulations are more moderate than in the previous case. However, it is noteworthy
463 that in both analyses the results are consistent in showing opposite FC patterns between groups.

464

465 *Task-induced modulations of segregation/integration reflect subjects' dexterity*

466 Our previous findings show that specific patterns of FC modulation from rest to movement depend
467 on the participants' motor skills (*i.e.*, performance on the 9-hole peg task). Based on past evidence of
468 motor learning inducing an increased segregation of the sensorimotor system and reduction of hub
469 centrality (Bassett et al., 2015), we estimated graph modularity in the α band by quantifying the
470 amount of segregation. We first applied a percolation analysis (Bordier et al., 2017) to obtain
471 individual binary graphs. Then, we applied the Louvain modularity (Lancichinetti and Fortunato,
472 2009) and ran a mixed model ANOVA on modularity, with Group (*High* and *Low performers*) as the
473 between-subject factor, and experimental condition (rest, hand motor task) as the within-subjects
474 factor. We found a significant interaction Group x Condition ($F_{1,45} = 20.46$, $p=0.00004$, $\eta^2=0.31$)
475 explained by an increase of network modularity when going from rest (fixation) to hand movements
476 (finger tapping) in *High* performers ($p=0.002$), and a decrease of modularity in *Low performers*
477 ($p=0.007$). Moreover, modularity in *High performers* was significantly smaller than *Low performers*
478 at rest ($p=0.03$), while it became larger than *Low performers* during finger tapping ($p=0.0002$) (Fig.
479 5A).

480 Then, we measured modulations of centrality through the participation index (PI, (Pasquale et al.,
481 2017)). Results obtained from a mixed model ANOVA with Group (*High* and *Low performers*) as a
482 categorical factor, experimental condition (rest, finger tapping) and RSNs (all networks) as within-
483 subject factors, revealed a significant interaction condition x Group x RSNs ($F_{9,405} = 2.84$, $p=0.003$,
484 $\eta^2=0.06$). When going from rest to task, *High performers* showed a significant decrease of the PI in
485 the Control Network (CON; $p=0.02$), Dorsal Attention Network (DAN; $p=0.04$) and MN
486 ($p=0.000007$). Conversely, *Low performers* showed a significant increase in DAN ($p=0.003$) and MN
487 ($p=0.04$). For sake of clarity, Fig. 5B shows difference between task and rest in the two groups. At
488 the level of individual regions (see methods), *High performers* showed a significant decrease of
489 centrality in nodes of the MN (dmSPL, vCS, S2, dPoCe, mdSPL), FPN (PrCu), DAN (mIPS) and AN
490 (mSTG). Conversely, *Low performers* showed significant PI increases in the MN (vPoCe, lvPoCe)
491 DAN (vPoCe-SMG, dPoCe, FEF), VAN (vPrCe, MFC2) and VFN (LO) (Fig. 5C).

492 In summary, when executing the finger-tapping task, dexterous individuals show an increase
493 in the segregation of the intrinsic network topology. In parallel, they show a reduction of centrality,
494 mainly in the MN, the DAN and the CON. The reduction of PI indicates that, during the finger-
495 tapping task, the connections underlying the hub centrality involve more within network connections
496 than across network ones. This suggests a “focusing” effect of the involved networks that reduce their
497 communication with other RSNs. Opposite patterns were found in *low* performers, with an increase
498 of across network communication mainly involving the DAN and MN.

499
500
501

502 **Discussion**

503

504 Manual dexterity is a long-term skill that varies among individuals, and this study investigated how
505 this characteristic is reflected in the task-induced modulation of spontaneous brain connectivity. We
506 confirmed that the underlying network topography observed at rest closely resembled that observed
507 during a motor task. However, in the α and β frequency bands, this stable topography combined with
508 consistent changes in connectivity strength and topology. Notably, in the α band, a specific
509 reorganization of connections enabled the differentiation of *High performers* from *Low performers*.
510 This reorganization manifested in opposite directions for the two groups: *High performers* displayed
511 primarily decreased motor network connections, while *low performers* exhibited more widespread
512 changes that extended beyond the motor network, with slight increases or greater stability. Notably,
513 *High performers* demonstrated an "internal focusing" effect in network topology. This was
514 characterized by increased network modularity, indicating enhanced segregation, and a decrease in
515 nodal centrality. Conversely, *Low performers* displayed an opposite trend, suggesting a dysfunctional
516 integration.

517 Proficiency in using hands reveals through specific modulations of functional architecture in
518 the α band. The functional significance of this rhythm is multifaceted and under debate. Traditionally,
519 its amplitude has been associated with the inhibition of task-irrelevant regions in the brain (Klimesch

520 et al., 2007; Jensen and Mazaheri, 2010). α is an “idling” rhythm (Pfurtscheller et al., 1996), *i.e.*,
521 denotes a state of inactivity of the brain circuits which is then de-synchronized during a task. The α
522 connectivity needs to be suppressed because more specific task-related functional patterns emerge
523 (Betti et al., 2013, 2018). Such an effect (Fig. 2, 2-2 and 2-3) is also in line with decrements of
524 correlated cortical noise occurring during tasks or stimulus presentation, observed in the monkey and
525 cat visual cortex (Smith and Kohn, 2008; Nauhaus et al., 2012). These α oscillations have been also
526 linked with high-order cognitive functions, such as memory and attention (Klimesch, 2012;
527 Sadaghiani and Kleinschmidt, 2016). They correlate with faster reaction times, better memory
528 performance, and information processing (Klimesch et al., 1993, 1996; Angelakis et al., 2004). A link
529 between α rhythm and behavior has been recently highlighted during resting-state, particularly in
530 expert populations. In a sample of pianists, the spontaneous phase coupling in the α band correlates
531 with the motor performance of finger-tapping (Allaman et al., 2020). Analogously, in expert dancers,
532 resting-state connectivity in the mu rhythm, successfully decodes the level of motor expertise
533 (Amoruso et al., 2017, 2022). Accordingly, motor (Albert et al., 2009; Tambini et al., 2010; Ma et
534 al., 2011; Taubert et al., 2011; Gabbitov et al., 2019) and perceptual learning (Lewis et al., 2009) shape
535 intrinsic connectivity in a behaviorally relevant manner. And, resting-state cortical connectivity
536 predicts future motor skill and visual perceptual learning acquisition (Baldassarre et al., 2012; Wu et
537 al., 2014; Dyck et al., 2021), and interindividual variability in motor performance (Roshchupkina et
538 al., 2022).

539 Our findings add novel information to this body of work.

540 In fact, although theoretical models predict that spontaneous connectivity reflects the training
541 of cortical networks in the course of development, first, and then daily life, most of the experiments
542 performed to-date adopted laboratory tasks (Harmelech and Malach, 2013; Betti et al., 2021; Pezzulo
543 et al., 2021). Here, we considered a finger tapping task, a controlled movement that closely resembles
544 the precision grip thumb-index (NAPIER, 1956; Castiello, 2005), used frequently and consistently
545 by people in daily life (Sili et al., 2023). Hence, one might argue that this movement, frequently

546 repeated during grasping of small objects, may be stored in patterns of intrinsic connectivity within
547 the motor cortex. We show that finger tapping differentially modulates α , not β , band connectivity in
548 motor cortex especially for participants displaying stronger manual dexterity in the 9-hole peg task.
549 There are two specific modulations. Firstly, higher dexterity participants showed regionally specific
550 decrements in the α band, especially in the motor network. Moreover, the connectivity changes were
551 more focal and segregated. Instead, lower dexterity individuals showed no changes in the motor
552 network and increased connectivity with more integration across networks. Secondly, toe squeezing,
553 a movement less frequently performed in daily life, caused a global and widespread reduction of the
554 intrinsic α connectivity across all networks.

555 The widespread connectivity decrements in α caused by the less practiced toe squeezing nicely
556 dovetails with our previous work in the visual system where we observed that natural stimuli
557 produced specific decrements in connectivity and temporal patterns of BLP correlation, that were
558 more limited and more similar to resting state topography, and dynamics than widespread changes
559 produced by synthetic temporally scrambled movies (Betti et al., 2018). The stronger similarity
560 between spontaneous dynamics and dynamics produced by natural stimuli vs. synthetic stimuli has
561 been also shown in single unit work in monkeys and ferrets (Fiser et al., 2004; Berkes et al., 2011).
562 We have argued that this similarity reflects the function of spontaneous activity as a spatiotemporal
563 generative model of the environment, body, and cognition (Pezzulo et al., 2021).

564 In contrast to α , β connectivity seems to be related to the movement itself, thus being highly
565 modulated during both motor tasks, without specific topographic changes (Fig. 2 and 2-3). Being β
566 the default rhythm of the motor system, task-induced modulations of connectivity may reverberate
567 even transiently after the task and correlate with motor learning (Mary et al., 2017). However, such
568 an effect is not shown here, as our study is not properly designed to explore the short-term training
569 effects.

570 In addition, we show that the level of long-term expertise in manual dexterity biases how the motor
571 network responds to a common motor task. Interestingly, higher performance individuals show more

572 segregation while lower performance individuals show more integration. This result has been
573 replicated in healthy subjects where stronger network segregation predicts higher cognitive, behavior,
574 and health performance (Smith et al., 2015), and in stroke patients where lesions cause abnormalities
575 of cognitive functions that linearly relate to the degree of modularity, and recover proportionally to
576 its improvement (Corbetta et al., 2018).

577 Previous studies showed that network segregation and integration mechanisms have been associated
578 with behavioral performance (Fornito et al., 2012; Cohen and D'Esposito, 2016; Wang et al., 2021).
579 In our study, in *High performers*, the required segregation seems to steer the system towards an
580 “internal focusing” of task-related networks. In fact, the segregation is observed through an increase
581 of functional modularity, going from rest to task. This agrees with previous studies where modularity
582 has been reported as sensitive to individual differences occurring during motor training (Bassett et
583 al., 2011; Baniqued et al., 2019). An increase in modularity during active motor behavior may
584 represent a strategy for responding more efficiently to the task demand. In fact, learned procedures
585 are automated (Milton et al., 2004) and characterized by focal brain activity (Pascual-Leone et al.,
586 1995; Krings et al., 2000; Kelly and Garavan, 2005). Specifically, we observed an increase in
587 modularity achieved through an important switch of the participation indices of functional hubs (Fig.
588 5). In *High performers*, hubs of the Motor and Control networks showed significant reduction of their
589 participation index when switching from rest to task. The observed trend in the participation index
590 suggests a shift in the role of the involved hubs from linking nodes of distinct communities to linking
591 nodes within the same community. This seems to realize the above mentioned “internal focusing” of
592 these RSNs. This is in line with previous studies, see for example (Shine et al., 2016). As far as it
593 regards *Low performers*, we observed an opposite reorganization of the functional architecture,
594 characterized by dysfunctional higher integration. Interestingly, the loss of network segregation has
595 been reported as a dysfunctional mechanism in many disconnection syndromes, such as stroke
596 (Spadone et al., 2022).

597 In summary, through the lifespan, learning processes and experience build an intrinsic
598 scaffold of communication that needs to be stable to store procedural and semantic memories.
599 However, in the presence of a task, it must also be flexible to enhance and support the performance.
600 Our study suggests that these properties are embedded in the topography and topology of the
601 modulation of the intrinsic connectivity in the α band. Jointly these observations suggest the
602 intriguing possibility that long-term priors may be coded in α connectivity, while short-term learning
603 in β connectivity. This hypothesis shall be tested in future experiments. Taken together, these results
604 suggest an intriguing novel role of the functional connectivity in the α band and its relationship with
605 behavior, well beyond the typically reported simple suppression.

606 Overall, our results pave the way for the development of novel and personalized therapeutic
607 strategies for restoring pathophysiological mechanisms arising from an impairment in the
608 coordination of distributed neural activity. This applies to a large variety of pathological disorders
609 ranging from traumatic and vascular lesions to neurodegenerative diseases (Hohenfeld et al., 2018).
610 For example, it has already been shown that stroke patients exhibit dysfunctional intra- and inter-
611 hemispheric connectivity patterns, and this impairment in the balance of communication can predict
612 behavioral impairment (Corbetta et al., 2018; Siegel et al., 2018). In this perspective, our results are
613 particularly relevant, as we provide evidence that dexterity, transversal to various motor
614 competencies, is already sculpted in neural communication. Intervening in these neural
615 communication patterns can allow us to develop recovery strategies with potential positive impacts
616 on daily living activities.

617

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809 **Author Contributions**

810 O.M, S.D.P., M.S, A.P., F.d.P., V.B. developed the pre-processing and analysis script. O.M.,

811 S.D.P., F.d.P., V.B. analyzed data. O.M, F.d.P., S.D.P., M.C., V.B. drafted the manuscript. All

812 authors revised the manuscript and approved its final version.

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824 **Figures, and captions**

825

826 **Figure 1. Experimental paradigm and analysis pipeline.** **A)** Participants performed a finger
827 tapping (with their right RH or left hand LH) or a toe squeezing (with their right RF or left foot LF).
828 The motor task consisted of 32 movement blocks (16 hand and 16 foot). Each block consists of 10
829 trials. 3 resting state runs lasting 6 minutes each precedes the motor task. **B)** A set of 164 node brain
830 parcellation, comprising 10 networks, is used to estimate the Band-limited power (BLP) in the alpha
831 (α , 8-15 Hz), beta low (β , 15-26 Hz) and beta high (26-35 Hz) band. **C)** The static functional
832 connectivity is calculated as the leakage-corrected correlation between each pair of nodes, separately
833 for the resting state and the task data. **D)** Linear model for the relationship between rest and task. A
834 K-means algorithm on the beta values of the model of each subject, identifies two groups (*i.e.*, *High*
835 and *Low performers*, blue and red). **E)** Measures of segregation/integration measures are computed.

836

837 **Figure 2. Changes of functional connectivity and topology induced by the finger tapping with**
838 **the right hand.** **A)** Group level difference connectivity matrices task-rest for alpha, beta low and beta
839 high bands. For visualization purposes, the matrices depict node to node correlation values. **B)**
840 changes of network topology. Right hand movements modulate fewer links in the alpha band,
841 especially within the motor network (green edges). Conversely, in the beta band we observed a wide-

842 spread topological reorganization across all networks. **C)** Percentage of modulated links. Within-
843 network connections are color-coded, between-network connections are shown in grey. See Figure
844 2-1, 2-2, 2-3 and 2-4 Extended data.

845
846 **Figure 3. K-means clustering identifies High and Low performers.** **A)** Centroids of the two
847 clusters, consisting of beta values, identified by K-means. **B)** Scatterplot depicting the linear
848 relationship between rest and task connectivity in the two groups (blue: *High performers*, red: *Low*
849 *performers*). A distinct linear trend is evident. **C)** The 2 groups differed in terms of manual dexterity.
850 The Dexterity Score was measured as mean RTs on the 9-hole peg test (see Materials and Methods).
851 The histogram for the Dexterity Scores is reported for *High* and *Low performers*. See Figure 3-1
852 Extended data.
853

854 **Fig 4. From brain-to-behavior and from behavior-to-brain approach: the modulation of**
855 **functional connectivity encodes manual dexterity** **A)** Difference (task-rest) connectivity matrices
856 for *High performers* (left panel) and *Low performers* (right panel). Only significant connections are
857 reported (t-test). *High performers* exhibit an overall decrease of FC in all networks, while *Low*
858 *performers* show a slight increase, with stability in the Motor Network. **B)** Modulation of topology
859 in *High* and *Low performers* and rate of re-organization expressed as percentage of modulated links.
860 Within-network connections are colored-coded, between-network connections are shown in grey.
861 **C)** As in panel A-B, we report the difference (task-rest) connectivity matrices for the *High*
862 *performers* (left panel) and *Low performers* (right panel) identified through median split on the
863 behavioral performance (9-hole peg test). According to the results extracted through the k-means,
864 *High performers* exhibit a decrease of FC, while *Low performers* show similarity between rest and
865 task matrices. **D)** Histogram for the Dexterity Scores for *High* and *Low performers*, according to
866 the median split procedure. See Figure 4-1.

867 **Fig 5. Functional integration and segregation in High/Low performers.** **A)** *High performers*
868 exhibit a statistically significant higher modularity during finger tapping than rest (* $p < 0.05$, **
869 $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$); conversely, modularity decreases in *Low performers* when switching from rest
870 to motor task. The different modularity in the two groups suggests that segregation relates to the
871 performance. **B)** The participation index shows a decrease of nodal centrality (averaged over nodes
872 in each RSN) in *High performers*, especially in the Motor, Control Network, and Dorsal Attention
873 Network. Conversely, in *Low performers*, the participation index increases. This modulation is
874 significant in Motor network and Control Network. **C)** Nodes with significant decreases in
875 Participation Index between rest and task in *High* (left) and increases of Participation Index in *Low*
876 *performers* (right). Here for visualization purposes are depicted differences in PI between task and
877 rest for each RSN. The statistically significant nodes are enlarged in the figure.
878

A)

B)

E)

D)

C)

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A)

B)

Topology

C)

Rate of reorganization

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A)

B)

C)

A)

Alpha right Hand

B)

Significant decreases

Significant increases

C)

D)

C) High performers (significant decreases)

Low performers (significant increases)

- Auditory Network (AN)
- Control Network (CON)
- Dorsal Attention Network (DAN)
- Default Mode Network (DMN)
- Fronto-parietal Network (FPN)
- Language Network (LAN)
- Motor Network (MN)
- Ventral Attention Network (VAN)
- Visual Foveal Network (VFN)
- Visual Peripheral Network (VPN)

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